

INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY (ICT)-BASED INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS IN TEACHING GRADE 10 MATHEMATICS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 29

Issue 6

Pages: 825-833

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2790

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14547148

Manuscript Accepted: 11-21-2024

Information and Communication Technology (ICT)-Based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of ICT-based Instructional Materials for Grade 10 at San Roque National High School - Antipolo City during the School Year 2019-2020. The study used descriptive method of research with the use of a survey questionnaire in terms of content, organization and presentation, language and style, modifiability, and user-friendliness. The ICT-based instructional materials were evaluated by ten (10) experts and ten (10) Mathematics teachers from different public schools of Antipolo City. Based on the findings, the Mathematics teachers and expert respondents Strongly Agreed that the developed ICT-based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics are acceptable shown by the overall weighted mean of 3.92 in terms of content, organization and presentation, language and style, modifiability, and user-friendliness. The study also used the experimental research method utilizing two-group pretest-posttest design to determine the effectiveness of the developed material. In addition, there was a significant difference in the pretest and posttest mean scores of the experimental group with the computed t value of 16.81. Moreover, there was a significant difference in the posttest mean scores of the participants from control and experimental groups with the earned mean of 17.07 and 22.23 and the computed t value of 5.05. This suggests that the ICT-based instructional materials had a positive impact on the experimental group's performance compared to the control group. Furthermore, the respondents gave their comments and suggestions which they believe can help the researcher in improving the material developed as it concerns the welfare of the students.

Keywords: *ICT, instructional materials, mathematics*

Introduction

The Philippines and other emerging countries particularly Asia and Africa are willing to learn about technological education, mainly about Information and Communication Technology (ICT), aiming that educational systems gain the educational profits associated with it. Exercise and training or software programming, for example, modifies instruction and offers students with immediate response.

Technology has made information, once a rare source, abundant. With the use of computers and internet technologies, people can easily access to additional information as fast as they can rather than before. Also, technology has exponential progress in access information that led to consistent exponential growth in production of new information, and it forced us to consider ideas that we need to learn and find out how we can learn from it.

As stated in the "Implementing Rules and Regulations of the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 (Republic Act No. 10533), Rule II Section 10.3 that pertains to the Production and Development of Materials ". The production and development of locally produced teaching and learning materials shall be encouraged. The approval of these materials shall be done by the regional and division education unit in accordance with national policies and standards.

Education in the Philippines is vital, more specifically in Mathematics. Statistics showed that the country stands far behind other countries in terms of international tests. In the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), the Philippines ranked last among 79 participating countries and economies in reading and second to last in science and mathematics (cnnphilippines.com, published Dec.3, 2019). Also, the Philippines ranked 67th of 140 countries in quality of math and science education in the 2015-2016 Global Competitiveness Report of the World Economic Forum, and 79th of 138 in the 2016-2017 data. (Dela Cruz, 2017).

The fact that mathematics still occupies one of the lowest ranks as revealed by the results of Global Competitiveness Report and PISA, mathematics teachers must cater to the needs of the development of the instructional devices and materials that can be used in teaching. The persistent necessity of improving the quality of instructional materials was knocking all the teachers in mathematics. As a Mathematics teacher, the researcher always experiences the students' lack of active participation which is one of the factors responsible for students' poor performance in the subject.

More so, the researcher as a three-year Math Grade 10 teacher had observed that for the past school years, 2018- 2019 and 2019-2020, the Mean Percentage Score (MPS) of the third quarter happened to be the lowest as shown in the Quarterly Test Results of 52.45 and 47.76, respectively. The least mastered skills based on the test result were the identify compound events and find its' probability, identify and find probability of union and intersection of events, and identify dependent and independent events and find its' probability. The least mastered skills were all about Probability, the topics were Probability of Compound Events, Union and Intersection of Events, and Independent and Dependent Events.

Thereby, one of the best ways to facilitate quality education is to develop a new instructional material that is fitted to the needs, abilities, understanding and interests of the students. With the above cited reasons on the positive impact of integrating technology in teaching

– learning process, the researcher is prompt to develop the Information and Communication Technology – based Instructional Materials in Mathematics for Grade 10 learners.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of ICT-based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics at San Roque National High School - Antipolo City during the School Year 2019-2020. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What was the evaluation of the Mathematics teachers and expert respondents on the developed ICT-based instructional materials in Mathematics 10 in terms of the following criteria:
 - 1.1. content;
 - 1.2. organization and presentation;
 - 1.3. language and style;
 - 1.4. modifiability; and
 - 1.5. user-friendliness?
2. What is the level of Grade 6 pupils' learning achievements using the user-centered word game-based approach in Science and Mathematics when they are categorized as:
 - 2.1. outstanding;
 - 2.2. very satisfactory;
 - 2.3. satisfactory;
 - 2.4. fairly satisfactory; and,
 - 2.5. did not meet expectations?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of pupils' learning achievements and the extent of utilization of user-centered word game-based approach in teaching Science and Mathematics?
4. Was there a significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed ICT-based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics in terms of the aforementioned criteria?
5. What was the level of performance of the experimental and control groups in Mathematics 10 as revealed by their pretest and posttest mean scores?
6. Was there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest mean scores of the control group?
7. Was there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest mean scores of the experimental group?
8. Was there a significant difference in the level of performance of the two groups of respondents as revealed by their posttest?
9. What were the comments and suggestions offered by the Mathematics teachers and expert respondents to further improve the ICT-based Instructional Material in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics?

Literature Review

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) take place in a widespread and essential play in the industrial revolution of education. ICT based instruction was a platform that supports the learning environment. This was due to its structure and benefits that affects the positively in teaching and learning process. This claim was supported by Nwigo (2016) in his journal entitled the Impact of ICT for Teaching and Learning Process. It revealed that ICT makes serves as the platform in facilitating the teaching and learning process, creates conducive learning environment and develop creative thinking and self-confidence to learners.

Goradia (2018) presented that the rapid development and innovation in information and technology, the challenges of the 21st century that need to fill in, the global inclinations in higher education are shifting towards in utilizing digital approaches. It was supported by the study of Koehler (2013) in which they developed the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework where the main purpose was to integrate technology in teaching. The study revealed a wide range of technologies and pedagogies being used to improve 21st century competencies and skills.

ICT can provide different options for taking in and processing information, making sense of idea and expressing learning in which can provide right skills for the learners with different styles of learning (Alsied, et al.,2015).

Stosic (2015), in his journal entitled The Importance of Educational Technology in Teaching, revealed that the teaching process is subjugated in traditional methods since computers are still not widely used in many schools. It is dominated by the front form of work where the teacher had enough communication with the students.

According to Dar's (2017) report, the Department of Education is now into implementing series of regional summits towards intensifying the use of Information, Communication and Technology (ICT) effective delivery of teaching and learning, and in the provision of efficient governance and operations directly to learners, teachers and relevant stakeholders in the field of education.

Consequently, Arias (2015), the rapid evolution of information and communication technology (ICT) is changing the face of education and making information universal. Realizing the effects of the ICT in the education system, the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) and Department of Education provided most of the schools with computer units and peripherals.

Furthermore, ICT integration in the lesson has great impact to the 21st century learners. This might have encouraged to develop material on the academic performance of students in line with ICT integration since it was found out it has a great impact to 21st century learners (Orlain, 2016).

Thus, initial readings have shown the importance of ICT in education, particularly in the context of the 21st century's demands for innovative learning experiences. Several studies emphasize the potential of ICT to enhance student engagement, cater to diverse learning styles, and facilitate independent learning. Research on ICT-based instructional materials in mathematics suggests that these tools can improve student performance and provide valuable support for teachers. The research also acknowledges the need for effective teacher training and technical support to ensure successful ICT integration in the classroom. These findings underscore the potential of ICT-based instructional materials to transform the teaching and learning of mathematics, fostering a more engaging and effective learning environment for students.

Methodology

Research Design

The study used descriptive method because its concern was to evaluate the developed instructional materials in the form of ICT-based in teaching Mathematics 10 in terms of content, organization and presentation, language and style, modifiability, and user-friendliness. According to Padua (2012), stated that descriptive method emphasizes at the current condition of person, events or class and may involve orientation, analysis, enumeration, classification, and measurement. The study also used the experimental research method utilizing two-group pretest-posttest design to determine the effectiveness of the developed ICT- based Instructional Materials in Teaching Mathematics 10. Blackstad (2015), experimental method of research is a collection of research designs which use manipulation and controlled testing to know fundamental processes. This is an experiment where the researcher manipulates one variable, and control/randomizes the rest of the variables.

Participants

The data in this study were gathered from the ten (10) experts and ten (10) Mathematics teachers from different public schools of Antipolo City. In addition, sixty (60) Grade 10 learners also served as respondents of this paper who gathered through purposive random sampling. The sections handled by the researcher were divided into two groups. The section Compassionate serve as the control group while the section Loyalty serve as the experimental group.

Instrument

The researcher analyzed the test results of the School Year 2017-2018 and 2018-2019 third grading period to identify the least mastered skills in order to develop an ICT-based Instructional Materials. The study used modified survey questionnaire to evaluate the said instructional material. The modified survey questionnaire was validated and evaluated by the school principal, Mathematics chairman, the research coordinator of San Roque National High School and the experts. The researcher used the pretest and posttest to determine the effectiveness of the developed ICT-based Instructional Materials in Grade 10 Mathematics.

Procedure

The researcher asked permission from the Division Office of Antipolo City to conduct the study to Grade 10 students at San Roque National High School S.Y 2019-2020. Then, the researcher developed the Information and Communication Technology (ICT)-based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics. Preparation of the pretest and posttest as well as the survey questionnaire. Validation of the instruments by the experts was done after.

The topics included in the material were the identified least mastered skills learning competencies from third grading period of the last two school years. The topics are the Probability of Compound Events, the Union and Intersection of Events, and the Independent and Dependent Events of Probability. The content of the ICT-based Instructional Materials includes different videos, simulated applications and power point presentations related to each learning competencies.

The researcher administered the survey questionnaire for the evaluation of the developed ICT-based Instructional Materials to the experts and teachers' respondents. After which, the researcher collects and analyzes the results of the evaluation. After the evaluation of the ICT-based Instructional Materials, the researcher administered the pretest for the set of respondents; thirty (30) for the control group and thirty (30) for the experimental group. The instructions were delivered before the respondents started with the ICT-based Instructional Materials. The researcher acted as a facilitator supervising the lesson proper for the experimental group and conventional teaching method for the control group. Then, the respondents accomplish the lesson properly. The researcher gave the posttest to measure if the ICT-based instructional materials given to the experimental group was effective. Lastly, the researcher treated, analyzed and interpreted the data gathered.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Evaluation of the Mathematics Teachers and Experts on the ICT-Based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics

Table 1. *Respondents' Evaluation on the Developed ICT-Based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics in Terms of Content*

<i>The content of ICT-Based Instructional Material...</i>	<i>Respondents</i>			
	<i>Teachers</i>		<i>Experts</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. is carefully organized and aligned with the prescribed competencies in Mathematics for Grade 10 Secondary Education Curriculum.	4.00	SA	4.00	SA
2. is clear and well presented.	4.00	SA	3.90	SA
3. helps students to understand and recall terms/concept easily.	3.90	SA	3.90	SA
4. is simple and comprehensible.	3.80	SA	3.80	SA
5. motivates the students to synthesize the concepts and effectively reinforce them to solve problem using mathematical skills.	4.00	SA	4.00	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.94	SA	3.92	SA
Standard Deviation	0.10		0.19	

It can be observed in Table 2 that the Mathematics teachers and expert respondents' evaluation on the developed ICT-based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics in terms of content is Strongly Agree as evidence by the overall weighted means of 3.94 and 3.92 with 0.10 and 0.19 standard deviations, respectively. This implies that the two groups of respondents Strongly Agreed in the contents of the ICT-based instructional materials. This may be due to the fact the lessons included in the developed ICT-based instructional materials covered topics in K to 12 Curriculum. The instructional material explained the learning goals, procedure and content clearly and accurately to the learners.

Table 2. *Respondents' Evaluation on the Developed ICT-Based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics in Terms of Organization and Presentation*

<i>The ICT-Based Instructional Material...</i>	<i>Respondents</i>			
	<i>Teachers</i>		<i>Experts</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. includes objectives that stated in behavioral terms.	4.00	SA	4.00	SA
2. presents topic headings that are clear and well-presented.	4.00	SA	4.00	SA
3. presents topics in logical and orderly sequences.	4.00	SA	4.00	SA
4. presents varied simulated application and multimedia that are enough to realize the objectives.	3.90	SA	3.80	SA
5. presents illustrations, figures and PowerPoint presentations that serve as instruments to attain the learning objectives.	4.00	SA	4.00	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.93	SA	3.96	SA
Standard Deviation	0.12		0.08	

It can be gleaned from Table 3 that the Mathematics teachers and expert respondents' evaluation on the developed ICT-based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics in terms of organization and presentation is Strongly Agree as evidence by the overall weighted means of 3.93 and 3.96 with 0.12 and 0.08 standard deviations, respectively.

Table 3. *Respondents' Evaluation on the Developed ICT-Based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics in Terms of Language and Style*

<i>The ICT-Based Instructional Material...</i>	<i>Respondents</i>			
	<i>Teachers</i>		<i>Experts</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. gives clear directions about the topic.	3.90	SA	3.90	SA
2. uses language that is suited to student's capability.	4.00	SA	3.90	SA
3. presents topics in logical and orderly sequence.	3.80	SA	3.90	SA
4. uses varied simulated application and multimedia that are enough to realize the objectives.	3.70	SA	3.90	SA
5. utilizes illustrations, figures and PowerPoint presentations which serve as instruments to attain the learning objectives.	4.00	SA	4.00	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.88	SA	3.92	SA
Standard Deviation	0.17		0.19	

This implies that the content offered in the ICT-based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics has characteristics which can be easily understood by the learners since it contains pictures, videos, simulated applications, quizzes, effects, transitions and guide which clearly presented in each topic and captured the attention of the learners for better understanding of the lessons.

It can be observed in Table 4 that the Mathematics teachers and expert respondents' evaluation on the developed ICT-based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics in terms of content is Strongly Agree as evidence by the overall weighted means of 3.88 and 3.92 with 0.17 and 0.19 standard deviations, respectively.

This implies that the language and style used in the developed ICT-based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics is appropriate to learners for it is clear and easily comprehensible, the ideas learned from the lesson can be applied and presented illustrations and applications to attain learning objectives.

Table 4. Respondents' Evaluation on the Developed ICT-Based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics in Terms of Modifiability

The ICT-Based Instructional Material...	Respondents			
	Teachers		Experts	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. characterizes self-contained/independence.	3.90	SA	3.90	SA
2. display information accurately.	4.00	SA	3.90	SA
3. allows modification if needed.	3.90	SA	4.00	SA
4. functions in simple manner.	3.80	SA	3.80	SA
5. can be accessed from one computer system or environment to another.	3.90	SA	3.90	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.88	SA	3.90	SA
Standard Deviation	0.14		0.25	

It can be seen on Table 5 that the Mathematics teachers and expert respondents' evaluation on the developed ICT-based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics in terms of modifiability is Strongly Agree as evidence by the overall weighted means of 3.88 and 3.90 with 0.14 and 0.25 standard deviations, respectively.

This implies that in terms of modifiability of the developed ICT-based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics is open and available. The teacher can select, prepare and utilize their methodologies and approaches towards the attainment of the learning objectives.

Table 5. Respondents' Evaluation on the Developed ICT-Based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics in Terms of User-Friendliness

The ICT-Based Instructional Material...	Respondents			
	Teachers		Experts	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. is user-friendly.	3.90	SA	3.90	SA
2. can be easily understood.	4.00	SA	3.90	SA
3. is significant and useful to the user.	3.90	SA	3.90	SA
4. performs its task/functions efficiently.	4.00	SA	3.90	SA
5. is easy to operate/manipulate.	3.90	SA	4.00	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.94	SA	3.92	SA
Standard Deviation	0.10		0.14	

It can be seen on Table 6 that the Mathematics teachers and expert respondents' evaluation on the developed ICT-based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics in terms of user-friendliness is Strongly Agree as evidenced by the overall weighted means of 3.94 and 3.92 with 0.10 and 0.14 standard deviations, respectively.

This implies that the developed ICT-based instructional materials are user friendly teaching material in Mathematics. Also, it can be easily operated and has directions that can be easily followed by the users.

Significant Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed ICT-based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics

Table 6. Test of Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed ICT-based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics in Terms of Content

Respondents	n	WM	sd	Computed t Value	Critical t value ($\alpha=5%$, $df=18$)	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	10	3.94	0.10	0.29	2.10	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
Experts	10	3.92	0.19				

As gleaned in the table, the critical t value with 18 degrees of freedom is 2.10 and the computed t value is 0.29. As the computed t value is less than critical t value, at the 5% level of significance, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. Hence, there is no significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed ICT-based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics in terms of content.

It implied that the Mathematics teachers and experts both agreed that the developed ICT-based Instructional Materials in teaching Grade 10 Mathematics can help improve the performance of the respondents as revealed in the content.

Table 7. *Test of Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed ICT-based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics in Terms of Organization and Presentation*

Respondents	n	WM	sd	Computed t Value	Critical t value ($\alpha=5\%$, $df=18$)	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	10	3.98	0.06	0.60	2.10	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Experts	10	3.96	0.08				

Based on the table, the computed t value of 0.60 is lower than the critical t value of 2.10, at the 5% level of significance, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, there is no significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed ICT-based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics in terms of organization and presentation.

This means that the Mathematics teachers and experts have the same evaluation that the developed ICT-based instructional materials in Grade 10 Mathematics was acceptable that it is view organized and the contents and activities are properly presented which can really help students in improving their competencies in Mathematics.

Table 8. *Test of Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed ICT-based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics in Terms of Language and Style*

Respondents	n	WM	sd	Computed t Value	Critical t value ($\alpha=5\%$, $df=18$)	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	10	3.88	0.04	0.49	2.10	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Experts	10	3.92	0.09				

Presented on table that the computed t value of 0.49 is lower than the critical t value of 2.10, at the 5% level of significance, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, there is no significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed ICT-based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics in terms of language and style.

It implied that the Mathematics teachers and experts have similar evaluation that the developed ICT-based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics was acceptable in improving the performance of the respondents as revealed in the language and style.

Table 9. *Test of Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed ICT-based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics in Terms of Modifiability*

Respondents	n	WM	sd	Computed t Value	Critical t value ($\alpha=5\%$, $df=18$)	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	10	3.88	0.14	0.22	2.10	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Experts	10	3.90	0.25				

Apparent from the table, the computed t value of 0.22 is lower than the critical t value of 2.10, so the null hypothesis is failed to reject. It concludes that the 5% level of significance that there is no significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed ICT-based

Instructional Materials in teaching Grade 10 Mathematics in terms of modifiability.

This means that the Mathematics teachers and experts have the same viewpoints that the developed ICT-based Instructional materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics can increase the performance of the respondents as revealed in the modifiability.

Table 10. *Test of Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed ICT-based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics in Terms of User-Friendliness*

Respondents	n	WM	sd	Computed t Value	Critical t value ($\alpha=5\%$, $df=18$)	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	10	3.94	0.10	0.37	2.10	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Experts	10	3.92	0.14				

As revealed in the table, the computed t value of 0.37 is smaller than the critical t value of 2.10, then the null hypothesis is failed to reject. It shows that there is no significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents at the 5% level of significance on the developed ICT-based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics in terms of user-friendliness.

This means that the Mathematics teachers and experts are one in point of outlooks that the developed ICT-based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics was acceptable since students will not find difficulty or even hard time understanding the activities as it suits to the level of the needs of these learners.

Level of Performance of the Experimental and Control Groups in Mathematics 10 as Revealed by the Pretest and Posttest

Table 11. *Performance of Control Group Based on the Pretest and Posttest Scores in Mathematics 10*

Performance of Control Group	Pretest		Posttest	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding (O)	0	0.00	2	6.67
Very Satisfactory (VS)	0	0.00	12	40.00
Satisfactory (S)	11	36.67	13	43.33
Fairly Satisfactory (FS)	17	56.67	3	10.00
Did Not Meet Expectation (DE)	2	6.67	0	0.00
Total	30	100.00	30	100.00

It was shown in the table that majority of the respondents from the control group performed fairly satisfactory as seen in the frequency of 17 out of 30 or 56.67% of the population. The highest level is satisfactory with 11 or 36.67% participants. Thus, after utilizing the conventional teaching, the number of participants with fairly satisfactory level reduced to 3 or 10%. Also, 12 very satisfactory and 2 outstanding students were produced.

This means that conventional teaching for control group was slightly improved the level of performance of Grade 10 learners in Probability.

Table 12. *Performance of Experimental Group Based on the Pretest and Posttest Scores in Mathematics 10*

Performance of Experimental Group	Pretest		Posttest	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding	0	0.00	13	43.33
Very Satisfactory	0	0.00	13	43.33
Satisfactory	10	33.33	4	13.33
Fairly Satisfactory	18	60.00	0	0.00
Did Not Meet Expectation	2	6.67	0	0.00
Total	30	100.00	30	100.00

It was revealed in the table that majority of the respondent from experimental group performed fairly satisfactory as seen in the frequency of 18 out of 30 or 60% of the population. The highest level is satisfactory with 10 or 33.33% participants. After using the developed ICT-based instructional materials, the number of participants with satisfactory level reduced into 4 or 13.33% participants. In addition, 13 very satisfactory and 13 outstanding students were produced.

It implied that the developed ICT-based instructional materials for experimental group improves the level of performance of Grade 10 learners who directly utilized the material in Probability.

Significant Difference in the Performance of Control Group Based on the Pretest and Posttest Scores in Mathematics 10

Table 13. *Significant Difference in the Performance of Control Group Based on the Pretest and Posttest Scores in Mathematics 10*

Test	n	Mean	SD	Computed t Value	Critical t value (α=5%,df=29)	Decision	Interpretation
Pretest	30	11.07	2.50	7.27	2.05	Reject the Ho	Significant
Posttest	30	17.07	4.18				

It can be seen in the table that the computed t value of 7.27 is greater than the critical t value of 2.05 at 0.05 level of significance and 29 degrees of freedom to conclude that there is a significant difference in the pretest and posttest score of the participants from the control group. The statement is justified in Table 16 in which after utilizing the conventional teaching, the number of participants with fairly satisfactory level decreased to 3 out of 30 but 12 very satisfactory and 2 outstanding students were produced.

It implied that the conventional teaching for the control group also help improved the level of performance of Grade 10 learners in Mathematics.

Significant Difference in the Performance of Experimental Group Based on the Pretest and Posttest Scores in Mathematics 10

It is revealed in the table that the computed t value of 16.81 is greater than the critical t value of 2.05, thus the statistical decision is to reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is enough evidence at 0.05 level of significance and 29 degrees of freedom to conclude that there is a significant difference in the pretest and posttest mean scores of the participants from the experimental group.

The statement is justified in Table 13 in which after using the ICT-based instructional materials, 13 very satisfactory and 13 outstanding students were produced.

Table 14. *Significant Difference in the Performance of Experimental Group Based on the Pretest and Posttest Scores in Mathematics 10*

Test	n	Mean	SD	Computed t Value	Critical t value ($\alpha=5\%$, $df=29$)	Decision	Interpretation
Pretest	30	10.50	2.33	16.81	2.05	Reject the Ho	Significant
Posttest	30	22.23	3.72				

It is revealed in the table that the computed t value of 16.81 is greater than the critical t value of 2.05, thus the statistical decision is to reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is enough evidence at 0.05 level of significance and 29 degrees of freedom to conclude that there is a significant difference in the pretest and posttest mean scores of the participants from the experimental group. The statement is justified in Table 14 in which after using the ICT-based instructional materials, 13 very satisfactory and 13 outstanding students were produced.

It strengthens that using the ICT-based instructional materials for the experimental group has greatly improved the level of performance of Grade 10 learners in Mathematics.

Significant Difference Between the Posttest Mean Scores of the Control and Experimental Groups

Table 15. *Significant Difference of the Mean Scores of the Two Groups of Respondents Based on the Posttest Scores*

Respondents	n	Mean	SD	Computed t Value	Critical t value ($\alpha=5\%$, $df=58$)	Decision	Interpretation
Control	30	17.07	4.18	5.34	2.00	Reject the Ho	Significant
Experimental	30	22.23	3.72				

It can be viewed in the table that the computed t value of 5.34 is greater than the critical value of 2.00, then the statistical decision is to reject null hypothesis. Thus, there is enough evidence at 5% level of significance and 58 degrees of freedom to conclude that there is a significant difference in the posttest score of the participants from control and experimental groups. It further revealed that the participants from control group earned a mean 17.07 while the respondents from experimental group earned a mean of 22.23.

Thus, it strengthens that using the ICT-based instructional materials for the experimental group was more effective than conventional teaching in improving the level of performance of Grade 10 learners in Mathematics.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following are the conclusions drawn from the results of the study.

The evaluation of the two groups of respondents on the developed ICT based instructional materials does not vary from each other.

Both Mathematics teachers and experts were agreed that the ICT-based Instructional Material in teaching Grade 10 Mathematics are acceptable in terms of content, organization and presentation, language and style, modifiability, and user-friendliness.

The experimental and control group increased performance after exposure to the develop ICT-based instructional materials and conventional method.

The developed ICT-based Instructional Materials in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics was more effective than the conventional method of teaching in improving the performance of the respondents.

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn, the following are recommended for the future study.

The developed ICT-based instructional materials should be validated for their further improvement.

Other levels of Mathematics department from San Roque National High

School may consider the least mastered skills/competencies in other quarters in developing ICT-based instructional materials in teaching Mathematics.

Future researchers may consider the least mastered skills/competencies in other quarters in Grade 10 Mathematics in developing other ICT-based instructional materials.

Future researchers should conduct parallel studies in other educational institutions to validate the findings of this research.

Future researcher should use qualitative feedback to ensure that all the survey questionnaires given to the respondents have comments or suggestions.

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